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HEMOLYTIC-URETIC SYNDROME CAUSED BY THE TOXIN OF SHIGA (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Introduction. *Thrombotic microangiopathies (TMAs) are a group of diseases characterized by microangiopathic hemolysis, thrombocytopenia, and thrombus formation leading to tissue damage. Traditionally, TMA has been classified as either thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura (TTP) or hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) based on clinical presentation, with the former predominating in neurological involvement and the latter in acute renal failure. [1]*

Key words: *microangiopathy, hemolysis, thrombocytopenic purpura, hemolytic uremic syndrome, pregnancy.*

The term thrombotic microangiopathy (TMA) refers to a group of diseases characterized by endothelial dysfunction and the formation of platelet- and fibrin-rich thrombi in small blood vessels. As the thrombus forms, consumption of platelets and mechanical destruction of erythrocytes occur, resulting in typical hematological manifestations of TMA, thrombocytopenia, and microangiopathic hemolytic anemia (formation of schistocytes, increased lactate dehydrogenase, and decreased haptoglobin).

Previously, TMAs were classified according to their clinical presentation with predominance of neurological symptoms in thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura (TTP) and acute kidney injury (AKI) in hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS). However, the clinical features of TTP and HUS overlap significantly, and the diseases are now classified based on etiology. [1,2]

The classification of hemolytic-uremic syndrome is more complicated, since the clinical picture corresponding to HUS can occur in a wide range of clinical scenarios. Most cases (90%) occur after infection with Shiga toxin-producing bacteria, enterohemorrhagic *Escherichia coli* (STEC) or *Shigella dysenteriae*, and usually affect children. The remaining 10% of cases are traditionally grouped as atypical HUS. It should be determined that atypical HUS is not one, but many different diseases with similar clinical signs. [3] TMA with a disease pattern consistent with hemolytic uremic syndrome can occur due to hereditary disorders, acquired diseases (including malignancies and autoimmune diseases), pregnancy, severe hypertension, and in response to medication. The situation is further complicated by the interaction between hereditary predisposition to diseases and environmental factors. As a result, there is still no generally accepted classification of GUS.

Hemolytic-uremic syndrome associated with Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC-HUS) belongs to the group of thrombotic microangiopathies, a heterogeneous group of diseases characterized by a triad of symptoms:

1. thrombocytopenia,
2. mechanical hemolytic anemia with schistocytosis,

3. ischemia of damaged organs. [3,4]

It is caused by gastrointestinal infection with Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* and is also called "typical" hemolytic uremic syndrome, as opposed to "atypical" HUS, which results from dysregulation of the alternative complement pathway, and "secondary" HUS, caused by various co-conditions

HUS associated with infection with Shiga toxin-producing bacteria (usually STEC HUS) is one of the most common causes of ARF in children, but can occur at any age. Although adaptive immune responses can be detected after exposure to enteropathogenic *E. coli*, it is unclear whether they are protective, and higher infection rates in children may be a consequence of more frequent exposure. [5]

Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* are highly infectious organisms. Most often, STEC infection occurs as a result of consuming contaminated food or water. Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* has a number of properties that increase its virulence. Inherent acid resistance allows you to survive through the acidic environment of the stomach. After passing through the stomach, STEC must colonize the intestinal mucosa; this is accomplished by a series of specialized proteins encoded at the enterocyte effacement locus and ultimately leads to attachment and effacement (A/E) lesions. These damages lead to the loss of microvilli and the accumulation of actin in the host cell, anchoring the bacteria to the surface. After adhering to the intestinal mucosa, STEC begin to produce Shiga toxin.[6]

Clinical features of hemolytic-uremic syndrome in children are diverse. Abdominal pain, diarrhea (with blood in 60%) and vomiting usually occur 3 days after ingestion of the bacteria. Approximately 10% of patients exposed to bacteria develop HUS. Both pathogen (inoculum size, pathogen strain, and type of toxin produced) and host-related factors (microbiome, motility disorders and antibiotic use, inflammatory response, and possible genetic factors) influence the development of HUS. 5–10% of patients with STEC HUS will have no history of diarrhoea, emphasizing the importance of microbiological examination of all patients with TMA, regardless of history.

Kidney damage is observed in most cases, dialysis is required in 50% of cases. Recovery of kidney function after 1–2 weeks is common, and end-stage renal disease (ESRD) after the initial presentation is rare. [7]

Neurological involvement is the most common extrarenal manifestation, with seizures and decreased level of consciousness reported in approximately one-third of cases. Other areas that can be affected include the intestinal tract and pancreas, the eyes, and the heart. The mortality rate in the acute phase of the disease is approximately 2–5% in STEC HUS, but is higher when HUS occurs after *Shigella* infection. Long-term renal complications are common, with hypertension and chronic kidney disease (CKD) occurring in 25–40% of patients.

Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* can colonize the intestines of healthy animals and enter the food chain if infected meat or other food products are consumed. Pathogenic *E. coli* binds tightly to the gastrointestinal mucosa, and the toxin is translocated across the epithelium into the circulation, where it binds to circulating erythrocytes and leukocytes. [5,6,7] The toxin, which consists of one A and five B subunits, binds to globotriaosylceramide (Gb3) on the surface of target cells. It is absorbed by endocytosis and then retrogradely transported to the endoplasmic reticulum. The A subunit inhibits protein synthesis, disrupting cell function and eventually leading to cell death. The toxin also causes an inflammatory reaction, the final effect of which is the establishment of a prothrombotic state in the microcirculatory channel. The cell surface concentration of Gb3 is particularly high in the kidney, not only on the endothelium, but also on podocytes and tubular epithelium. This may explain the susceptibility of the kidney to damage, but other factors, such as high renal blood flow, may also contribute. [8]

Fecal culture should be performed in all patients with TMA, regardless of the presence of a history of colitis. The diarrhea may have stopped by the time of presentation, but bacteria can still be isolated, so a stool or rectal swab should still be sent. PCR can be performed on these samples to detect the presence of Shiga toxin genes. Positive serology for antibodies against toxin-producing *E. coli* serotypes confirms the diagnosis of STEC HUS, although it is not routinely used. [8,9]

There is currently no evidence that treatment other than supportive care, including dialysis and mechanical ventilation as needed, improves outcomes in patients with STEC HUS. The role of antibiotics is controversial, and their use has traditionally been avoided due to concerns that antibiotic treatment leads to greater release of Shiga toxin, increasing the likelihood and severity of STEC HUS. Certain antibiotics, such as macrolides and fosfomycin, reduce toxin synthesis and may reduce the risk of HUS. [9]

Eculizumab is a humanized monoclonal IgG2/4 that binds C5, preventing its conversion to C5a and C5b. Preventing this step effectively blocks the formation of the final complement pathway. Eculizumab was first approved in 2007 for use in paroxysmal nocturnal hemoglobinuria and subsequently in 2011 for the treatment of aHUS. Recent studies have shown that it is

effective and safe for the treatment of aHUS in both adults and children, although there is a significantly increased risk of meningococcal infection due to terminal complement blockade. [10]

Conclusion: Hemolytic-uremic syndrome can develop in response to a number of different triggers and in different clinical situations. Determining the cause of HUS can be difficult, but very important, as treatment and prognosis depend on accurate and timely diagnosis.

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